

Stress and its Risk Factors in Acute Myocardial Infarction: a cross-sectional study

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El estrés y sus factores de riesgo en el infarto agudo de miocardio: un estudio transversal

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Received: 05/20/2022 Accepted: 08/19/2023 Published: 09/25/2023 DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10027874>

Abstract

Introduction: The current study was performed to examine the prevalence rate of perceived psychological stress in patients diagnosed with acute myocardial infarction in an Iraqi sample population. In addition, the predictors of stress in this group of patients were determined through the statistical analysis.

Methods: In the current cross-sectional study, a total of 50 patients were diagnosed with acute myocardial infarction (MI) and admitted to the coronary care unit were recruited purposively. The diagnosis of MI was established according to the World Health Organization (WHO) criteria. The stress level of patients was measured by Perceived Stress Scale (PSS), a structured scale anchored on a 5-point Likert scale; low stress (PSS: 0-14), moderate stress (PSS: 15-26), and high stress (PSS: 27-40).

Results: The mean age of 50 patients who were recruited in the present study was 60.52 years (SD: 12.16, Range: 29-86). The majority of the patients were recognized to have a moderate or severe level of stress (76%). The patients with lack or a lower level of education and live in rural areas had significantly a higher level of stress. The statistical calculations did not show any predictor for the stress in patients with myocardial infarction.

Conclusions: The level of stress in the study sample was very high requiring a special stress management strategies for these types of patients.

Keywords: stress, risk factors, acute myocardial infarction

Resumen

Introducción: El presente estudio se realizó para examinar la tasa de prevalencia del estrés psicológico percibido en pacientes diagnosticados de infarto agudo de miocardio en una muestra de población iraquí. Además, se determinaron los predictores del estrés en este grupo de pacientes mediante el análisis estadístico.

Métodos: En el presente estudio transversal, se reclutó de forma intencionada a un total de 50 pacientes diagnosticados de infarto agudo de miocardio (IM) e ingresados en la unidad de cuidados coronarios. El diagnóstico de IM se estableció según los criterios de la Organización Mundial de la Salud (OMS). El nivel de estrés de los pacientes se midió mediante la Escala de Estrés Percibido (PSS), una escala estructurada anclada en una escala Likert de 5 puntos; estrés bajo (PSS: 0-14), estrés moderado (PSS: 15-26) y estrés alto (PSS: 27-40).

Resultados: La edad media de los 50 pacientes reclutados en el presente estudio fue de 60,52 años (DE: 12,16, Rango: 29-86). A la mayoría de los pacientes se les reconoció un nivel de estrés moderado o severo (76%). Los pacientes que carecían de estudios o tenían un nivel educativo inferior y vivían en zonas rurales presentaban un nivel de estrés significativamente superior. Los cálculos estadísticos no mostraron ningún factor predictivo del estrés en los pacientes con infarto de miocardio.

Conclusiones: El nivel de estrés en la muestra de estudio fue muy elevado requiriendo unas estrategias de manejo del estrés especiales para este tipo de pacientes.

Palabras clave: estrés, factores de riesgo, infarto agudo de miocardio

Cardiovascular diseases are one of the three main factors responsible for mortality along with cancer and stroke in the developed countries^{1,2}. Close to 1.5 million persons present with acute myocardial infarction (AMI) in the USA³. World Health Organization (WHO) reported that the cardiovascular diseases are increasing constantly and predicted to reach 46.4% by 2010². This disease does not only impacts the patients' health but also influence the social and familial relationships and occupation^{4,5}.

Myocardial infarction (MI) is considered as a serious health condition resulting in significant morbidity and mortality in different populations. About one-third of the affected patients present with sudden death as their first clinical manifestation⁶. The disease as a life-threatening and inestimable medical condition can trigger significant distress in patients both during and after the onset of acute myocardial infarction^{7,8}. Inability to control, uncertainty feelings and helplessness are reported commonly in patients following the disease onset^{9,10}.

Several factors could have a role in increasing risk of affliction with MI. The factors may include: diabetes mellitus, obesity, hyperlipidemia, physical inactivity, age, sedentary behaviors, family history and psychological factors such as stress^{11,12}. Of the mentioned risk factors, stress may play a critical role in the incidence of acute MI and its subsequent complications^{13,14}.

Stress can be defined as physical, mental, and emotional responses experienced by a person owing to life alterations and personal life needs¹⁵. The affective health of the patients diagnosed with MI is impaired in addition to impacts on cardiovascular condition. Also, the recovery of patients is prolonged owing to the prevalence of the psychosomatic condition in these patients. Therefore, it is imperative to understand the level and predictors of stress in MI patients. The current study may be a guide for the clinicians to effectively meet the needs of patients in clinical settings. In particular that there is an evident gap in this disease.

The present study was performed to explore, the prevalence of perceived stress in a sample of patients diagnosed with acute myocardial infarction as well as, to examine the socio-demographic and clinical predictors of stress.

Patients and Methods

Study design and sampling

In the present cross-sectional study, a total of 50 recently diagnosed patients with acute myocardial infarction and admitted to the coronary care unit at Azadi Teaching Hospital in Duhok-Iraqi Kurdistan were recruited between 1st Jan 2017 and 1st April 2017. The patients were selected purposively through the review of the medical records of the patients.

The patients met the eligibility criteria if they were male or female, aged 45 years and older, irrespective of socio-demographic aspects. The patients with unstable conditions or did not show a willingness to participate were excluded from the study. In addition, the patients with severe medical and psychological conditions who were not able to understand the questions along with those patients with aggravation of psychological disorders over the last six months were excluded.

The interview and extraction of medical records were performed following taking ethical approval from the Scientific Division of Department of Planning of Duhok General Directorate of Health. In the present study, the patients did not undergo any intervention and the participation was completely optional. The patients were given complete guarantee of confidentiality of their personal information.

Diagnostic and measurement criteria

The baseline information of the patients such as age (measured in the year) and gender (scaled as male or female) were obtained through the self-reported technique or they were extracted from the medical records of patients. The Body Mass Index (BMI) was measured in dividing weight in Kg by square root of the height in meter. The BMI of less than 18.5 was considered as underweight, BMI between 18.5 and 24.9 as normal weight, between 25.0 and 29.9 as overweight, and greater than 30 as an obese patient.

The diagnosis of MI was established by a cardiologist according to the criteria of World Health Organization (WHO), including typical chest pain symptoms plus either an increase in cardiac enzyme concentrations or typical diagnostic changes as measured by an electrocardiogram. The patients must show the clinical evidence to support the AMI diagnosis, including prolonged ischemic signs and symptoms for 20 minutes or changes in electrocardiographic ST-segment during the first 24 hours of hospital admission¹⁶.

The perceived stress level of the patients was measured by Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) through the direct interview with the patients². The PSS measures the degree of stressful situations experienced by a person. The scale enables to detect low unpredictable, uncontrollable, and overloaded respondents in the personal life. The scale measured the stress level through direct

queries on current levels of stress experienced by a person. The questions are general and non-specific to any sub-group. The scale questions include asking the people to state their feeling and thoughts since the last month. It has 10 items measure the feeling according to a 5-point Likert scale rated 0 (never), 1 (almost never), 2 (sometimes), 3 (fairly often), and 4 (very often). In this scale, the score of items 4, 5, 7, and 8 are reversed as 0=4, 1=3, 2=2, and 4=0. The scores are added together and a total score is obtained between 0 and 40. The higher score means higher perceived stress. A low level of stress is established in score between 0 and 13, moderate between 14 and 26, and severe stress between 27 and 40¹⁷.

Statistical methods

The descriptive purposes of the study such as the prevalence of stress in MI patients were determined by frequency distribution and the continuous characteristics in mean and standard deviation. The predictors of stress level were examined through the univariate analysis of variance. The statistical calculations were performed in Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 24:00. The null hypothesis was rejected with P-value of less than 0.05.

The mean age of 50 patients recruited in the present study was 60.52 years (SD: 12.16, Range: 29-86). The study revealed that the majority of the patients were males (72% vs. 28%) in 50-64 age group (48%). The male: female ratio was 2.57:1. Most of them were illiterate (50%), married (8%), employed (40%), from urban areas (68%) and of low socioeconomic status (74%), see Table 1.

In addition, the majority of the patients had a high level of stress with a moderate or severe status (76%), were overweight (43%), physically inactive (68%), with less than 6 hours of sleeping (44%), and never alcohol consumers (92%), same table.

Table 1: Socio-demographic and clinical characteristics of patients

Variables (n=50)	Frequency	
	No.	(%)
Gender (Male/Female)	36/14	72/28
Age (Years)		
< 50	8	16
50-64	24	48
≥ 65	18	36
Educational level		
Illiterate (0 years)	25	50
Primary (1-6 years)	14	28
Secondary (7-12 years)	7	14
Higher (≥13 years)	4	8
Marital status		
Married	44	88
Single	3	6
Widow	3	6
Occupation		
Employed	20	40
Retired	12	24
Housewife	12	24
Unemployed	6	12
Residence		
Urban	34	68
Rural	16	32
Socioeconomic status		
Low	37	74
Moderate	13	26
High	0	0
Level of stress		
Low	12	24
High (Moderate/Severe)	38	76
Smokers	24	48
BMI		
Underweight	0	0
Normal	15	30
Overweight	24	43
Obese	11	22
Exercise		
No	34	68
Irregular	14	28
Regular	2	4
Sleep		
< 6 hours	22	44
6-8 hours	21	42
> 8 hours	7	14
Alcohol consumption		
Never	46	92
Regularly daily	2	4
Irregularly (Occasionally)	2	4
Chronic medical diseases	34	68

The relation of socio-demographic aspects with stress levels was examined in Table 2. The study showed that patients with different gender ($P=1.00$), age groups ($P=0.248$), whether married or not ($P=0.137$), employed or not ($P=0.818$), and with different socio-demographic status ($P=0.376$) were comparable in stress levels. However, the study revealed that the illiterate patients

or those with a lower level of education and live in rural areas (P=0.048 and P=0.042, respectively) were more likely to be affected by the moderate or severe level of stress (See table 2).

Socio-demographic perspectives (n=50)	Level of stress		P-Value (two-sided)
	Low	High (Moderate/ Severe)	
Gender Male Female	9 (25) 3 (21.4)	27 (75) 11 (78.6)	1.000**
Age (Years) < 50 50-64 ≥ 65	3 (37.5) 7 (29.2) 2 (11.1)	5 (62.5) 17 (70.8) 16 (88.9)	0.248*
Educational level Illiterate (0 years) Primary (1-6 years) Secondary (7-12 years) Higher (≥13 years)	3 (12) 4 (28.6) 2 (28.6) 3 (75)	22 (88) 10 (71.4) 5 (71.4) 1 (25)	0.048*
Marital status Married Single Widow	10 (22.7) 2 (66.7) 0 (0)	34 (77.3) 1 (33.3) 3 (100)	0.137*
Occupation Employed Retired Housewife Unemployed	6 (30) 2 (16.7) 3 (25) 1 (16.7)	14 (70) 10 (83.3) 9 (75) 5 (83.3)	0.818*
Residence Urban Rural	11 (32.4) 1 (6.3)	23 (67.6) 15 (93.8)	0.042**
Socioeconomic status Low Moderate	8 (21.6) 4 (30.8)	29 (78.4) 9 (69.2)	0.376**

*Pearson Chi-Square and ** Fisher's Exact Test were performed for statistical analyses.

The **bold numbers** show the significant difference.

Similarly, the relation of clinical characteristics of the patients with stress level was examined in Table 3. The study showed that the patients whether smoker or not (P=0.745), had a normal or non-normal weight (P=0.871), physically active or not (P=0.572), do sleep 6 hrs or less (P=0.782), alcohol consumers or not (P=0.447), and had a chronic disease or not (P=0.414) were similar in stress level.

Clinical characteristics (n=50)	Level of stress		P-Value (two-sided)
	Low	High (Moderate/ Severe)	
Smoking No Yes	7 (26.9) 5 (20.8)	19 (73.1) 19 (79.2)	0.745**
BMI 18.5-24.9 25-29.9 ≥ 30	4 (26.7) 6 (25) 2 (18.2)	11 (73.3) 18 (75) 9 (81.8)	0.871*
Exercise No Irregular Regular	7 (20.6) 4 (28.6) 1 (50)	27 (79.4) 10 (71.4) 1 (50)	0.572*
Sleep < 6 hours 6-8 hours >8 hours	6 (27.3) 4 (19) 2 (28.6)	16 (72.7) 17 (81) 5 (71.4)	0.782*
Alcohol consumption Never Regularly daily Irregularly (Occasionally)	10 (21.7) 1 (50) 1 (50)	36 (78.3) 1 (50) 1 (50)	0.447*
Chronic medical diseases Yes No	9 (26.5) 3 (18.8)	25 (73.5) 13 (81.3)	0.414**

*Pearson Chi-Square and ** Fisher's Exact Test were performed for statistical analyses.

The socio-demographic and clinical aspects of the patients were considered as predictors (independent factors) and the stress level as the dependent variable and univariate analysis of variance was performed in Table 4. The study did not show the stress level is predicted through socio-demographic and clinical characteristics (P>0.05).

Dependent variable: Stress Level (n=50)				
Predictors	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared (Effect Size)
Gender	0.085	0.573	0.478	0.087
Residency	0.056	0.376	0.562	0.059
Marital	0.049	0.329	0.732	0.099
Education	0.063	0.425	0.742	0.175
Occupation	0.030	0.206	0.889	0.093
Smoking	0.009	0.059	0.816	0.010
BMI	0.003	0.021	0.979	0.007
Physical Activity	0.058	0.390	0.693	0.115
Sleeping	0.000	0.003	0.997	0.001
Alcohol consumption	0.033	0.225	0.805	0.070
Medical conditions	0.013	0.090	0.775	0.015
Age	0.215	1.451	0.340	0.848

The authors' aim in the present study was to examine the prevalence of perceived stress and its predictors in a sample population of patients diagnosed with acute myocardial infarction in Iraqi Kurdistan. The study detected a high level of stress with the moderate or high level of stress (76%) and the remaining (24%) with a low level of stress. Moreover, the study showed that the stress is more prevalent in patients with a lack/lower level of education and those living in rural areas.

The present study is supported by the literature. Goldfeld, Soares studied the levels of stress and stressful life events in post-MI patients who underwent cardiac catheterization. They compared between patients who were presented with symptoms suggestive of MI without history of previous cardiac insult and patients who had no. The study found that the patients diagnosed with MI have stress OR= 5.37(95% CI, 2.94–9.78, $p<.001$), while cardiac catheterization group showed OR=9.18 (95% CI, 4.73–17.82, $p<.001$) in comparison with the control group. They showed that the stress is increased after adjustment with age sex, and physical inactivity¹⁸. We could not find the predictors in this study, possibly because of small sample size. It is hard to obtain information from the patients with acute MI owing to the high load of the clinical settings and the patients' instability. Lucinda, Prosdócimo found that 72.1% of the patients presented with Acute myocardial infarction had stress¹⁹.

Arnold, Smolderen found that of the total 4204 patients discharged from the hospitals, 1622 (38.6%) were recognized with moderate or high levels of perceived stress following 4 weeks of AMI onset. In addition, Arnold, Smolderen showed that the higher stress levels were associated with younger age, more likely to be female, unmarried, with a low level of social support, and non-adherence to medications, and more likely to complete high school. Moreover, the patients with higher levels of stress were hypertensive, diabetic, smokers, obese, and depressive²⁰. The discrepancies between findings reported in the present investigation and those reported in other studies can be explained by the study design, sampling, and assessment tool as the cross-sectional study does not allow to make justification on a causal pathway. In addition, the number of patients participated in this study was lower than comparison with the mentioned above study.

The urban areas are stressfully exerting more physical and psychological pressure on patients. However, the higher substantial stress was reported in those patients living in rural areas in this study. We were unable to relate this finding to one or more aspects of patients, as it may be related to the disease severity rather than socio-demographic aspects.

Stress has been considered one of the factors has a substantial role in the incidence of acute MI and its subsequent complications¹³. Therefore, the health policy-makers and hospital directors should guide their patients to the appropriate coping mechanism. A reduced level of stress has been correlate to the higher level of education of the patients with cardiovascular conditions²¹. Chronic stress outside the context of depressive symptoms was shown to associate with adverse outcomes. The patients with a moderate/higher level of stress have been associated with an increased risk of 2-year mortality in comparison with those recognized as lower stress (12.9% vs. 8.6%; $p 0.001$) even after adjustment of socio-demographics, clinical features, revascularization status, and GRACE (Global Registry of Acute Coronary Events). These kinds of patients had 1-year poor health status recognized in a higher likelihood of angina, worse disease-specific and general health status ($P=0.01$)²⁰. Vujcic, Vlajinac showed that 77.9% of the patients diagnosed with AMI have general stress compared to 52.3% in controlled ($P<0.001$)²².

Chronic stress has been contributing to both the development and progression of cardiovascular disease²³ and cardiovascular death^{24,25}. The mechanism in the mentioned relation pathway is complex, however, it has been assumed multi-factorial. Several factors may include, such as smoking, lack of physical activity, obesity²⁶, non-adherence to medications, high blood pressure, and pulse rates²⁷. The present study showed that the lack or lower education level is a factor to have a higher level of stress. It may be explained with the fact that the lower educated patients are unaware of the protective factors implementing through the self-management strategy. Hence, these patients must be educated in stress management through their involvement in training courses.

Other risk factors have been mentioned in the literature to have a role in a higher level of stress, such as physical inactivity²⁸ and deaths and diseases, family-related stressful events, work-related stressful events, and financial problems²². It is important that these factors should be considered in the subsequent risk of disease severity, recovery, and future complications.

Although the exact mechanism of the stress associated with adverse outcome in these patients is unknown, it is crucial to consider the stress and its bad effects on health status and poor long-term outcomes. We could not measure the short or long-term outcomes in these patients owing to time restriction of the clinicians and non-availability of patients following the hospital discharge.

In the evaluation of stress area, it is important to consider the external factors as they could have a vital role in events onset and social support of the patients. In particular that the country faced disaster and civil war since the last 4 years which emphasize the importance of community-based interventions.

Implications

According to the current evidence of stress level in patients with AMI and its prognostic role in disease complications, it presents an opportunity to assess the patients and establish evidence-based strategies. The investigators in the next attempt would concentrate on the impact of perceived stress on AMI complications in this region.

Limitations of the study

The strengths and weaknesses of the present investigation must be traced in the inherence of study design, sampling, and the number of participants. The cross-sectional study precludes us to establish a cause and effective pathway. In addition, the sample selected for the present study was taken from one clinical area which prevented generalization of the findings to other settings in the rest of the country. However, the significance of the study comes from determining that patients with MI have a higher level of stress encountering them with subsequent psychological effects. The small sample size used in this study did not allow us to determine the predictors of stress.

Conclusions

The present study showed that the stress is a prevalent condition in patients with acute MI in this region. The study found that the patients with a lack of lower level of education and live in rural areas had a greater level of stress. The patients require behavioral medicine to manage the stress and its adverse effects on recovery and subsequent disease complications.

Acknowledgments: The authors of the study would like to present their deep gratitude to the patients who participated in the study and the kind cooperation of Azadi Teaching Hospital.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare that there is no any conflict of interest.

Funding: The researchers were only financial supporters of the study.

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